

Identification of Bioactive Secondary Metabolites and Screening of Antitumor and Antimicrobial Activities of *Ginkgo biloba* L. (Kabar Oo leaves)

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Abstract

This research deals with the investigation of bioactive secondary metabolites and screening of antitumor and antimicrobial activities of *Ginkgo biloba* L. (Kabar-Oo) leaves. The *G. biloba* leaves sample collected from Pyin Oo Lwin Township, Mandalay Region was firstly subjected to screen the phytochemicals present, to determine the nutrition values and some soluble matter contents, and to isolate some organic constituents followed by structural identification. Isolation and identification of some phytoconstituents and screening of antitumor, antioxidant, anticancer and antimicrobial activities of the sample were carried out. Firstly, four compounds (**A**, **B**, **C** and **D**) from *G. biloba* leaves was isolated by thin layer and silica gel column chromatographic methods. Compound **A** (tetradecan-1-ol, 0.006 %, m.pt 38-40°C) and compound **B** (a mixture of β -sitosterol & stigmasterol, 0.005 %, m.pt 138-140 °C) were isolated from PE crude extracts and compound **C** (ginkgetin, 0.008 %, m.pt 336-338 °C) and compound **D** (bilobetin, 0.007 %, m.pt 296-298 °C) obtained from EtOAc extract of *G. biloba* leaves. As the second part, some biological screening was done on some extracts as well as isolated compounds. These isolated compounds were identified by some physicochemical tests, melting point, solubility tests, colour test on TLC, UV and FT IR, ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectroscopic methods. Antimicrobial activity of five different extracts (PE, EtOH, EtOAc, MeOH, CHCl₃) of *G. biloba* leaves was determined by agar well diffusion method. Antimicrobial activity screening by agar well diffusion method showed that ethyl acetate extracts possessed the pronounced activity against *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, *B. pumilus*, *C. albicans* and *E. coli* with the inhibition zone diameters between 24 ~ 46 mm than other extracts. Antitumor activity was determined by potato crown gall (PCG) assay revealing that EtOH, EtOAc and MeOH extracts and isolated compounds inhibited tumor growth produced by *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* in a concentration dependent manner. Significant tumor growth inhibition was observed at 0.2 g/mL of the extracts and 0.2 µg/mL of the isolated compounds. The research finding exhibited that *Ginkgo biloba* (Kabar-Oo) leaves have the very high potency in antimicrobial and antitumor activities.

Keywords : *Ginkgo biloba* L. (Kabar-Oo), tetradecan 1-ol, β -sitosterol & stigmasterol, bilobetin, antimicrobial activity, antitumor activity.

Introduction

In the early development of modern medicine, biologically active compounds from plants have played a vital role in providing medicines to combat diseases. Plant-derived medicines continue to occupy an important niche in the treatment of diseased worldwide. In the present work, locally grown *G. biloba* leaves was selected to investigate some biologically active constituents and anticancer activity due to lack of scientific report on these two locally cultivated medicinal plants. *Ginkgo* scientifically known as *Ginkgo biloba* L. is of the plant family Ginkgoaceae. Genus is *Ginkgo* and species is *biloba*. Myanmar name is Kabar-oo tree. Other common names are *Ginkgo*, Maidenhair tree, Yin xing (Chinese), Ichu (Japanese) (Nakanishi, 2005). *Ginkgo biloba* is found growing wild around Ahijiang in Eastern China and in the Tian Mu Shan Reserve. The first mentioned medicinal use of *Ginkgo biloba* appears in China.

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The leaves of Ginkgo used for the treatment of Dementia, Alzheimer's disease, Asthma, Allergies, Anxiety, Cerebrovascular insufficiently, Stroke recovery, Depression and Cancer. Chemical constituents present in the medicinally used leaves are the terpene trilactones, i.e., ginkgolides A, B, C, J and bilobalide, many flavonol glycosides, biflavones, proanthocyanidins, alkylphenols, simple phenolic acid, 6 hydroxykynurenic acid 4-O-methylpyridoxine and polyprenols (Rossi *et al.*, 2011).

Figure 1. Photographs of *G. biloba* tree and leaves

Experimental

The sample was collected selected medicinal plants in this study was *G. biloba* (Kabar Oo). The leaves of *G. biloba* (Kabar Oo) was collected from Botanical Garden, Pyin Oo Lwin Township, Mandalay Region during September, 2012 . Preliminary phytochemical tests on the sample was carried out according to the appropriate reported methods. The nutrition values such as (moisture, ash, fibre, protein, fat and carbohydrate contents) from leaves of *G. biloba* was determined by AOAC method.

The following instruments were used for structure elucidation of isolated compounds: Gallenkamp melting point apparatus, Shimadzu UV-1800 UV visible spectrophotometer (Department of Chemistry, University of Yangon), FT IR 8400 Fourier Transformed infrared Spectrophotometer (Amtt Co.Ltd, Yangon), ^1H NMR (600 MHz) and ^{13}C NMR(125 MHz) Spectrometer (Department of Organic and Biomolecular Chemistry, Georg-August University, Goettingen, Germany) and 2D NMR (600 MHz) Spectrometer (Graduate School of Bioagricultural Sciences Nagoya University, Japan). Column chromatography was performed using Silica gel 60, 0.063-0.200 mm (70-230 mesh, ASTM) (Merck, Germany), and precoated TLC plates (GF₂₅₄ Aluminium plates, Merck) was applied for thin layer chromatography. All solvents were purified by distillation at their boiling point ranges.

The crude extracts of sample was isolated by silica gel column chromatographic method using silica gel column chromatographic method using silica gel (40-60 μm). The PE extract (6.5 g) of *G. biloba* leaves was separated by column chromatography over silica gel, solvent system PE : EtOAc (40:1 to 1:4 v/v) to give compound **A** (0.006%, 30 mg) and compound **B** (0.005 %, 26 mg), EtOAc extract (2g) was also separated by column chromatographic method, eluting successively with PE:EtOAc(40:1 to 1:2 v/v) and EtOAc : MeOH (1:4 and 17:1) give compound **C** (0.008 %, 40 mg) and compound **D** (0.007 %, 33 mg). The isolated compounds (**A-D**) were characterized by determination of some physical properties such as melting points, R_f values and solubility and some chemical properties by some colour tests. Some pharmacological activities such as antimicrobial activity, antioxidant

activity, antitumor activity and anticancer (or) cytotoxicity activity of some crudes extracts and some isolated compounds of the leaves of *G. biloba* in *in vitro*. The structure of isolated compounds **A-D** were elucidated and identified by modern spectroscopic techniques such as UV, FT IR, ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR, 2D NMR and EI MS spectroscopy.

Screening of antimicrobial activity of leaves of *G. biloba* by agar disc diffusion method

The screening of antimicrobial activity of various crude extracts such as PE, EtOAc, 70 % EtOH, CHCl_3 and MeOH extracts of *G. biloba* leaves was carried out by agar disc diffusion method at Fermentation Laboratory, Pharmaceutical Research Department, Ministry of Industry, Yangon, Myanmar. Six microorganisms namely *Bacillus subtilis* (JAP-022/215), *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC-12277), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (IFO-3080), *Bicillus pumilus* (IFO-12102), *Candida albicans* (IFO-1060) and *Escherichia coli* (ACCT-25922) were used for this test.

Screening of anti-tumor activity

Anti-tumor activity of ethanol and ethyl acetate extracts and some isolated compounds was examined by Potato Crown Gall (PCG) (or) Potato Disc Assay (PDA) method (Ferrigni *et al.*, 1982) at Fermentation Laboratory, pharmaceutical Research Department, Ministry of Industry, Yangon, Myanmar.

Results And Discussion

Types of Phytochemicals Present in *G. biloba* L. Leaves

In order to find out the types of phytochemical constituents that present in *G. biloba* leaves, phytochemical tests was preliminarily carried out according to the procedure.

According to these result, it was observed that alkaloids, carbohydrates, saponins, steroids, glycosides and terpenoids are present while and cyanogenic glycosides are absent in *G. biloba* leaves. Moreover flavonoids, organic acids and α -amino acids are present in the leaves of *G. biloba*.

Some Nutritional Values of *G. biloba* Leaves

The determination of nutritional values by AOAC method indicated that the percentage concentration of moisture, ash, fibre, protein, fat and carbohydrate contents. According to the results, 12.5 % of moisture, 10.0 % of protein, 9.09 % of fat , 10.20 % of ash, 29.37 % of fibre and 28.8 % of carbohydrate were found in leaves of *G. biloba*. The energy content were determined to be 237 kcal/100 g for the *G. biloba* leaves.

Organic Solvents and Water Soluble Matter of Leaves of *G. biloba*

The soluble matter contents in some organic solvents such as PE, EtOAc, CH_3COCH_3 , EtOH and H_2O were found to be 57.9, 33.8, 45.8, 87.6, 59.8 mg/g in the leaves of *G. biloba*.

Table 1. Phytochemical Results of the Leaves of *G. biloba*

No.	Tests	Extract	Test Reagent	Observation	KO
1	Alkaloids	dil HCl	Mayer's reagent Dragendorff's reagent Wagner's reagent	White ppt Orange ppt Reddish brown	+ + +
2.	α -Amino acid	H ₂ O	Ninhydrin reagent	Pink spot	+
3.	Carbohydrates	H ₂ O	10 % α -Naphthol & Conc H ₂ SO ₄	Red ring	+
4.	Cyanogenic glycosides	H ₂ O	Sodium picrate	No Brick red ppt	-
5.	Flavonoids	EtOH	Conc HCl and Mg turning	Pink colour	+
6.	Glycosides	H ₂ O	10% Lead acetate	White ppt	+
7.	Organic acids	H ₂ O	Bromocresol blue indicator	Blue colour	+
8.	Phenolic compd.	EtOH	10% FeCl ₃	Dark Blue	+
9.	Polyphenolic Compounds	H ₂ O	1% Potassium ferricyanide and 1% ferric chloride	Green colour	-
10.	Reducing sugars	H ₂ O	Fehling's A and Fehling's B	Brick red	-
11.	Saponins	H ₂ O	Distilled Water	Frothing	+
12.	Steroids	PE	Acetic anhydride and Conc H ₂ SO ₄	Greenish blue	+
13.	Terpenoids	CHCl ₃	acetic anhydride and Conc H ₂ SO ₄	Pink or red colour	+

(+) present,

(-) absent

KO = *G. biloba*

Compound A (tetradecan-1-ol)

White needle, $C_{14}H_{30}O$, R_f 0.4, UV-inactive; FT IR ν_{max}/cm^{-1} ; 3315, 3218, 2954, 2865, 1464, 1377-1344; 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 0.83, δ 1.29 & δ 1.40, δ 3.59. According to FT IR, 1H NMR spectral data, compound A was deduced as tetradecan-1-ol (Figure 2,3,4).

Figure 2. FT IR spectrum of isolated compound A

Figure 3. 1H NMR spectrum (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) of isolated compound A

Figure 4. Chemical structure of tetradecan-1-ol ($C_{14}H_{30}O$)

Compound B (β -sitosterol)

Colourless needle, $C_{29}H_{50}O$ (mpt 138-140°C), R_f 0.5, UV inactive; FT IR ν_{max}/cm^{-1} ; 3549, 3294 for ν_{OH} , 3025 for ν_{CH_2} & ν_{CH_3} group, 2935 for ν_{CH} , 1634 for $\nu_{C=C}$, δ_{CH} of CH_2 and CH_3 group appeared at 1458 cm^{-1} (Figure 4). The 1H NMR spectrum of isolated compound **B** (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) is shown in (Figure 5). A one proton doublet at δ 5.36 was attributed to =CH proton (H-6). A methane proton of CH-OH group was found at δ 3.53 as a multiplet. Four doublets at δ 0.93, 0.84, 0.83 and 0.81 ppm integrated that CH_3 groups. The observed FT IR and 1H NMR spectral data of compound **B** were also studied by comparing with those of reported β -sitosterol

Figure 5. FT IR spectrum of isolated compound B

Figure 6. 1H NMR spectrum (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) of isolated compound B

Figure 7. Chemical structure of β - sitosterol ($C_{29}H_{50}O$)

Compound C (Isoginkgetin)

Yellow powder (mpt 353-355 °C), $C_{32}H_{22}O_{10}$, R_f 0.46, UV active; the band with maximum absorption bands at λ_{max} 217 and 327 nm indicating the presence of conjugated double bond. The UV spectrum exhibited maxima at 277 and 370 nm in the presence of MeOH and NaOH suggestion to possess phenolic-OH group (Figure 8). FT IR ν_{max}/cm^{-1} ; 3544, 3292, 1350, 1168, 2921-2850, 1495, 1424, 1651, 1604, 1573, 1238 (Figure 8); 1H NMR; δ 3.8 and δ 3.7 for 3H in-OCH₃ group, δ 6.2 ($J = 1.6$ Hz) due to the phenyl protons, δ 8.03 ($J = 2.4$ Hz) due to four phenyl protons, δ 8.17 ($J = 2.4$ and 8.8 Hz) attributed to methine proton attached with an oxygen atom, δ 6.8 ($J = 9.2$ Hz and 2.8 Hz) and 6.9 ppm ($J = 9.2$ Hz and 2.8 Hz) were due to two methylene protons adjacent to methine proton (Figure 10).

1H 1H COSY spectrum of isolated compound C is shown in Figure 11. The signals at δ 6.5, 6.8, 6.9, 7.33, 7.6 and 8.17 were observed in 1H 1H COSY spectrum. In addition aromatic methine protons at δ 7.6 (d, 9.6, H-2'' and H-6'') were coupled with the other methine protons of δ 6.9 (d, 9.2, H-3'' and H-5''). So the isolated compound C possesses 22 protons.

The ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO) spectrum of isolated compound C is shown in Figure 11. The spectrum revealed the presence of thirty two carbon signals including thirteen aromatic methane δ 94.4-182.4 ppm, two carbonyl groups δ 56.2 (C-4'), 55.8 (C-4''), four oxygenated aromatic carbon δ 160.7 (C-4'), 103.97 (C-10''), 131.1 (C-2'), 162.5 (C-4''), eight quaternary carbons. All of these ^{13}C NMR data were coincident with these of reported isoginkgetin compound. Above spectral data, compound C was deduced as isoginkgetin compound ($C_{32}H_{22}O_{10}$).

From EI MS spectrum (Figure 15), the spectral data of isolated compound C indicated the presence of a molecular ion peak $[M + H]^+$ at m/z 567. All of the above mentioned 1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR, COSY, HMBC, HSQC and EI MS spectral data were consistent with those of reported isoginkgetin (Marcelo *et al.*, 2014) that the structure can be illustrated as shown in Figure 16.

Figure 8. UV spectra of isolated compound C
 (a) MeOH, NaOAc and H_3BO_3 (Absorbance)
 (b) MeOH, $AlCl_3$ and HCl (Absorbance)

Figure 9. FT IR spectrum of isolated compound C

Figure 10. ¹H NMR (600MHz, CDCl₃, CD₃OD) spectrum of isolated compound C

Figure 11. ¹³C NMR (125MHz, CDCl₃/CD₃O) spectrum of isolated compound C

Figure 13. ¹H-¹H COSY (600 MHz, CDCl₃ /CD₃OD) spectrum of isolated compound C

Figure 12. ¹H-¹H COSY (600 MHz, CDCl₃/CD₃OD) spectrum of isolated compound C

Figure 13. HSQC (600 MHz, CDCl₃ /CD₃OD) spectrum of isolated compound C

Figure 14. HMBC (600 MHz, CDCl₃ /CD₃OD) spectrum of isolated compound C

Figure 15. EI MS spectrum of isolated Compound C

Figure 16. Chemical structure of isolated compound C

Compound D (Bilobetin)

Yellow powder (mpt 296-298), Rf 0.39, UV active; revealed the absorption maxima (λ_{max}) 205 nm, 270 nm and 335 nm in methanol indicating the presence of phenolic O-H group due to π - π^* transition (Figure 17).

The FT IR spectrum of isolated compound **D** is shown in Figure 18. The absorption band at 3545 cm^{-1} , 3292 cm^{-1} were due to O-H stretching of alcoholic and phenolic O-H groups while O-H bending was appeared at 1350 cm^{-1} . The absorption band at 1602 cm^{-1} was due to C=C stretching of alcoholic and phenolic O-H groups. The band at 2921 - 2850 cm^{-1} showed asymmetric and symmetric C-H stretching vibration of CH_2 group and their C-H bending vibration occurred at 1365 cm^{-1} . The band at 1648 cm^{-1} showed the stretching vibration of α, β -unsaturated carbonyl group. The band at 1505 cm^{-1} suggested the stretching C-O-C in Ar-O group.

The $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectrum (600 MHz, CDCl_3) of compound **D** is shown in Figure 18. The proton signal at δ 3.8 revealed the presence of O- CH_3 group. The doublet at δ 6.69 ($J = 2.0\text{ Hz}$) was due to the phenyl protons which were *meta*-coupled to each other on ring A. Two doublets at δ_{H} 8.04 ppm ($J = 2.0\text{ Hz}$) were due to four phenyl protons situated at 2',3',5',6' position of ring B. A doublet of doublet at δ 8.18 ppm ($J = 2.4$ and 8.8 Hz) was attributed to methine proton attached with an oxygen atom and another two doublets of doublet at δ 6.2 ($J = 9.2\text{ Hz}$ and 2.8 Hz) and 6.69 ($J = 9.2\text{ Hz}$ and 2.8 Hz) were due to two methylene protons adjacent to methine proton of ring C.

From EI MS spectrum (Figure 20), the spectral data of isolated compound **D** indicated the presence of a molecular ion peak [M - H] at m/z 553 which corresponding to the molecular $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_{10}$. All of the above mentioned UV, FT IR, $^1\text{H NMR}$, and EI MS spectral data were consistent with those of reported bilobetin (Junxia *et al.*, 2007) and the structure is illustrated in Figure 21.

Figure 17. UV spectra of isolated compound **D**
 (a) MeOH, NaOAc and H_3BO_3 (Absorbance)
 (b) MeOH, AlCl_3 and HCl (Absorbance)

Figure 18. FT IR spectrum of isolated compound **D**

Figure 19. $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectrum of compound **D** (600MHz,

Figure 20. EI MS spectrum of isolated compound D

Figure 21. Chemical structure of isolated compound D

Antimicrobial activity of crude extracts of *G. biloba* leaves

Five crude extracts of *Ginkgo biloba* leaves such as PE, EtOAc, EtOH, MeOH, CHCl₃ extracts was screened for antimicrobial activity against six different pathogenic microbes.

From the results, it was observed that PE, CHCl₃, MeOH extracts of *G. biloba* leaves and PE did not show any antimicrobial activity against all of the microorganisms tested. Six microorganism with the inhibition zone diameter ranged 24-36 mm for EtOAc, 16-20 mm for EtOH extracts of ginkgo leaves, (Figures 22,23). According to the results, EtOH and EtOAc extracts of *G. biloba* leaves possessed pronounced activity against Gram positive, Gram negative bacteria, and fungus.

Figure 22. Photo records showing inhibition zone due to the effect of different crude extracts of *G. biloba* leaves

Figure 23. Histogram showing antimicrobial activity of different extracts of *G. biloba* leaves

Antitumor activity of *G. biloba* leaves

Antitumor activity in this study was investigated by potato crown gall (PCG) assay as it is a valuable tool that indicates antitumor activity of test compound by their inhibition crown gall formation that was induced in wounded potato tissues by *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*.

- (a) Control (before treating with Lugol's solution)
 (b) Control (after treating with Lugol's solution)
 (c) 0.2 g of ethanol extract from *G.biloba* (before treating with Lugol's solution)
 (d) 0.2 g of ethanol extract from *G.biloba* (after treating with Lugol's solution)
 (e) 0.4 g of ethanol extract from *G.biloba* (before treating with Lugol's solution)
 (f) 0.4 g of ethanol extract from *G.biloba* (after treating with Lugol's solution)
 (g) 0.2 g of EtOAc extract from *G.biloba* (before treating with Lugol's solution)
 (h) 0.2 g of EtOAc extract from *G.biloba* (after treating with Lugol's solution)
 (i) 0.4 g of EtOAc extract from *G.biloba* (before treating with Lugol's solution)
 (j) 0.4 g of EtOAc extract from *G.biloba* (after treating with Lugol's solution)

Figure 24. Photographs of tumor inhibition by the leaves of *G. biloba* extracts

(c)

(d)

- (a) 0.2 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of isolated compound A from *G. biloba* (before treating with Lugol's solution)
- (b) 0.2 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of isolated compound A from *G. biloba* isolated compound (after treating with Lugol's solution)
- (c) 0.4 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of isolated compound C from *G. biloba* (before treating with Lugol's solution)
- (d) 0.4 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of isolated compound C from *G. biloba* (after treating with Lugol's solution)

Figure 25. Photographs of tumor inhibition by the isolated compound (A+C) of *G. biloba*

Table 2. Tumor Inhibition by the Crude Extracts and Isolated Compounds of *G. biloba* Leaves

No	Test Sample	Concentration	Tumor
		(g/mL)	
<i>Ginkgo biloba</i> Leaves	Control	-	-
	EtOH extract	0.2	+
	EtOH extract	0.4	+
	EtOAc extract	0.2	+
	EtOAc extract	0.4	+
	EtOH extract	0.2	+
	EtOH extract	0.4	+
	EtOAc extract	0.2	+
	Compound A	0.2 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	+
	Compound B	0.2 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	+

(-) tumor appeared (+) no tumor appeared

Conclusion

From the present anticancer activity of the leaves of *G. biloba* and identification of active compounds, the following inferences can be drawn. Preliminary phytochemical investigation revealed that alkaloids, carbohydrates, saponins, steroids, and glycosides are present while cyanogenic glycosides are absent in *G. biloba* leaves. Moreover, flavonoids, terpenoids, steroids, organic acids and α -amino acids are present in the leaves of *G. biloba*. The nutritional values determined by AOAC method indicated that the content % of protein, moistures, ash, fibre, fat, carbohydrate in the leaves of *G. biloba* were 10.0, 12.5, 10.2, 29.4, 9.1 and 28.9. The energy contents was determined to be 237 kcal/100 g for the leaves of *G. biloba*. On silica gel column chromatographic separation, four compounds : tetradecan 1-ol (A, 0.006%, m.pt. 38-40°C), β sitosterol (B, 0.007 % , m.pt. 138-140 °C), isoginkgetin (C, 0.008 % , m.pt. 353-355 °C), bilobetin (D, 0.007 % , m.pt .296-298°C)were isolated from *G. biloba* leaves. The isolated compounds were characterized by some physical and chemical properties and structurally identified by the combination of UV, FT IR, ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR, 2D NMR and EI MS spectroscopic methods and also by comparing with the reported data. Antimicrobial activity of five different extracts (PE, EtOH, EtOAc, MeOH, CHCl_3) of *G. biloba* leaves was determined by agar well diffusion method. Test microorganisms were *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, *B. pumilus*, *C. albicans* and *E. coli*. EtOH and EtOAc extracts of *G. biloba* leaves showed the higher antimicrobial activity than other extracts of these leaves. Antitumor activity investigated by potato crown gall (PCG) assay revealed that EtOH, EtOAc and MeOH extracts and isolated compounds tetradecan 1-ol and isoginkgetin inhibited tumor growth in a concentration dependent manner.

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